

Horizon Scanning Pilot Exercise Regarding One Health

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Various international and national organizations have addressed that foresight studies regarding One Health are of interest. Strategic foresight methods are needed to help different stakeholders to plan for the future. Horizon scanning is a qualitative technique/method for detecting early signs of potentially developments through the assessment of potential threats and opportunities, which has the potential to be applied as a foresight tool.

METHODS

The pilot foresight exercise was based on an assembly of information sources and an assembly of analysis teams with assigned topics. Within the One Health EJP project COHESIVE, a horizon scanning team of composed experts within public health, animal health, food safety has been performed. To explore the potential application of such a technique, a pilot horizon scanning exercise took place during the autumn of 2019. The pilot exercise first identified more than 30 potential One Health issues. From these a summary of six topics were identified to have a key impact in the next coming years.

RESULTS

Some examples of One Health Long List:

Elderly people, immunity status, early detection of signals, consumer behaviour, urbanization, wild life, migration, governance, vaccine availability, unknown pathogens/threats, global transportation, geopolitical instability, water sources, environment/warmer climate, new food trends, disasters, wild life, use of fertilizers .

Final List of One Health Drivers:

- Political and decision making behaviour
- People and consumer behaviour
- Science and innovations
- Market behaviour
- New and re-emerging pathogens/threats
- Climate change

Fig 1 Horizon scanning technique, modified according to Wintle et al 2017 (<https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.30247>)

CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVES

The conducted pilot horizon scanning exercise showed to be useful but needs to be further developed for foresight applications related to one health in Europe. The One Health pilot horizon scanning exercise took place (nov 2019) prior the covid-19 pandemic. Even though the foresight was focused on one health the exercise identified many issues that have been of relevance during the last months.

This poster is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.